

Tailless Aircraft Control Law Design Using Dynamic Inversion & μ -synthesis

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Abstract

In this paper, a manual flight control system for the combined longitudinal and lateral-directional dynamics of a tailless fighter airplane is presented. The design method used is dynamic inversion combined with structured singular value synthesis to address the issues of stability, performance, and robustness to plant uncertainties. Design objectives are formulated in terms of stability, flying qualities, and robustness achieved by the closed-loop system. The controller structure consists of an inner loop in which equalizes the airplane dynamics across the flight envelope and an outer loop having a robust dynamic controller to provide the tracking performance.

1. Introduction

Due to its configuration, the tailless fighter aircraft dynamics are tightly coupled and highly non-linear. Any yaw motion tends to be accompanied by a pitch motion. This coupling behavior requires the controller to consider the aircraft dynamics in all three axes at the same time. The non-linear nature of the fighter can be addressed with the dynamic inversion approach. The inner loop control uses dynamic inversion to linearize the plant to give it the desired dynamics. These desired dynamics are maintained throughout the flight envelope so that the fighter's modified dynamic responses are similar in the whole envelope. The dynamic inversion controller is a static gain matrix that is updated according to the changing flight condition. Imperfect inversion and parameter variations can be considered as the uncertainties associated with the closed, inner-loop plant. An outer-loop controller is formed around the inner-loop to meet performance requirements and to address these uncertainties. The μ -synthesis approach naturally lends itself to the outer loop problem formulation.

2. The Tailless Airplane

New requirements for military airplanes has led to a tailless fighter design with a number of new control concepts in different configurations. The new control effectors being studied are the all-moving-tips (amt), differential leading edge flaps (lef), spoiler-slot deflector (ssd), deployable rudders along with pitch thrust vectoring (ptv) and yaw thrust vectoring (ytv). Different fighter configurations make use of different combinations of the above control effectors. The airplane configuration chosen has the left elevon (*le*), right elevon (*re*), pitch flaps (*pf*), left all-moving-tip (*lamt*), right all-moving-tip (*ramt*), pitch thrust vectoring (*ptv*), and yaw thrust vectoring (*ytv*) as shown in Figure 1. The present investigation focuses on the all-moving-tip as a yaw control device. Yawing moment is created by induced drag. The non-linear, six degrees of freedom dynamic simulation of the airplane is implemented in FORTRAN code. The flight envelope from which the linear models are obtained covers Mach number from 0.2 to 0.6 at the altitude of 0 to 20,000 feet. The usual linear model of a dynamic system:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x} = Ax + B\delta \\ y_{sens} = Cx \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

is obtained by linearizing the non-linear equations in a trim flight and has the following structure:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{\alpha} \\ \dot{q} \\ \dot{\beta} \\ \dot{p} \\ \dot{r} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Z_{\alpha} & \dots & Z_p & Z_r \\ M_{\alpha} & \dots & M_p & M_r \\ Y_{\alpha} & \dots & \sin\alpha & -\cos\alpha \\ L_{\alpha} & \dots & L_p & L_r \\ N_{\alpha} & \dots & N_p & N_r \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ q \\ \beta \\ p \\ r \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} Z_{le} & Z_{re} & \dots & Z_{ptv} & Z_{ytv} \\ M_{le} & M_{re} & \dots & M_{ptv} & M_{ytv} \\ Y_{le} & Y_{re} & \dots & Y_{ptv} & Y_{ytv} \\ L_{le} & L_{re} & \dots & L_{ptv} & L_{ytv} \\ N_{le} & N_{re} & \dots & N_{ptv} & N_{ytv} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \delta_{le} \\ \delta_{re} \\ \delta_{pf} \\ \delta_{lamt} \\ \delta_{ramt} \\ \delta_{ptv} \\ \delta_{ytv} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

Figure 1: Tailless Airplane

$$\text{and } y_{sens} = [\alpha \ q \ \beta \ p \ r]^T.$$

Linear models at different points in the envelope are used for the inner-loop design. In the outer-loop, the model at the mean dynamic pressure in the envelope is used. This model is called the central model. The eigenvalues of the central model are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Open-Loop Eigenvalues

Eigenvalues λ	Damping ζ	Frequency ω (Rad/Sec)
0.436	-1	0.436
-0.572+j0.765	0.599	0.955
-0.5721-j0.765	0.599	0.955
-0.618+j0.748	0.6370	0.971
-0.618+j0.748	0.637	0.971

3. Design Objectives

Our controller performance is evaluated by its ability to provide the flying qualities while performing the design task of tracking a command. The flying quality specifications used in this design are obtained from MIL-STD-1791A [7]. To achieve the flying qualities, the dampings ζ , frequencies ω and time delay τ in Table 2 should be met:

Table 2: Req: Longitudinal, Time Delay

Flying Quality Level	Longitudinal (Short Period Mode)			Max Delay $\tau_{\theta, \mu}$ sec.
	ω_{sp} rad/rec	ζ_{sp} min. max.		
	1	$\omega \geq 1.0$	0.35	1.3
2	$\omega \geq 0.6$	0.25	2.0	0.2

Robustness to both structured and unstructured uncertainties are also required of the controller. Actuators and sensors uncertainties are usually modelled as

Table 3: Req: Lateral-Directional

Flying Quality Level	Lateral-Directional (Dutch Roll & Roll Modes)		
	ω_d rad/rec	ζ_d	T_r max.
	1	$\omega_{d,min.} \geq 1.0$	$\zeta_{d,min.} \geq 0.40$
2	$\omega_{d,min.} \geq 0.6$	$\zeta_{d,min.} \geq 0.02$	1.4

unstructured uncertainty with high-pass filters whose magnitudes reflect the amount of uncertainties. In contrast to the unstructured certainties whose origins are not clearly identified, structured uncertainties are generally caused by the variations of some parameters such as the change in cg location. The shifting of the airplane center of gravity during flight affects C_{M_x} which in turn affects the stability derivatives in Equation 2. Using the amount of uncertainties suggested in [1] for the F-16, the parameter uncertainty bounds on the stability derivatives can be seen in Table 5.

4. Controller Design

Designing controller consists of two tasks. The first task is to equalize the airplane dynamics throughout the flight envelope via the dynamic inversion method and an appropriate control selector. The dynamic inversion controller and the control selector can modified according the airplane's flight condition. With the airplane dynamics equalized, the second task involves finding a single controller that will satisfied the required performance and robustness.

4.1. Inner Loop Design

In the inner loop, we attempt to modify the plant dynamics at different flight conditions to the desired dynamics using the dynamic inversion method. The control variables that most affect the dominant, fast dynamics of the system are the control variables we would like to make uniform across the flight envelope. Generally, these control variables are the plant states or their linear combinations. For the airplane, the states associated rotational rates q, p , and r around the three body-axis X, Y, Z respectively are normally the fast dynamics of the vehicle. The angle of attack α also strongly affects the dynamics of the vehicle. Therefore in the longitudinal dynamics the control variable named M_{cv} is chosen to be a blend of the pitch rate q and the angle of attack α :

$$M_{cv} = q + 0.1\alpha \quad (3)$$

$$L_{cv} = p \quad (4)$$

$$N_{cv} = r \quad (5)$$

4.1.1 Control Selector: We want to find a transformation called CS such that $B \cdot \delta = CS \cdot \delta^*$ where

$$\delta = [\delta_{le} \ \delta_{re} \ \delta_{pf} \ \delta_{lamt} \ \delta_{ramt} \ \delta_{ltv} \ \delta_{rtv}]^T$$

and

$$\delta^* = [M\dot{C}V \ L\dot{C}V \ N\dot{C}V]^T$$

From Equation 1, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} B \cdot \delta &= B^* \cdot \delta^* \\ B \cdot N \cdot \tilde{\delta} &= B^* \cdot \delta^* \\ \tilde{\delta} &= (B \cdot N)^{\#} \cdot B^* \cdot \delta^* \\ \delta &= N \cdot (B \cdot N)^{\#} \cdot B^* \cdot \delta^* \\ \delta &= CS \cdot \delta^* \end{aligned}$$

where the control selector CS is,

$$CS = N \cdot (B \cdot N)^{\#} \cdot B^* \quad (6)$$

Here N is a control redistribution matrix that we can use in case of overlapping control effectiveness. As seen in Equation 6, the control selector CS is a function of the plant control derivatives which, in turn, are functions of Mach and altitude. To update the control selector CS with changing flight conditions, values of the control derivatives for various trim flight conditions are stored in a data base for later computation. From Equations 3, 4, 5, we have

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{M}_{cv} \\ \dot{L}_{cv} \\ \dot{N}_{cv} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{q} + 0.1\dot{\alpha} \\ \dot{p} \\ \dot{r} \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

From Equations 2 & 7, the generalized control variables have the following dynamics:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{M}_{cv} \\ \dot{L}_{cv} \\ \dot{N}_{cv} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} M_{\alpha} + 0.1Z_{\alpha} & \cdots & M_r + 0.1Z_r \\ L_{\alpha} & \cdots & L_r \\ N_{\alpha} & \cdots & N_r \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \\ r \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} M_{le} + 0.1 \cdot Z_{le} & \cdots & M_{ytv} + 0.1 \cdot Z_{ytv} \\ L_{le} & \cdots & L_{ytv} \\ N_{le} & \cdots & N_{ytv} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \delta \quad (8)$$

In this design, we choose N to be an identity matrix. A judicious choice of N can be made based on the actuators' rate limits, position limit, and other requirements. Since we would like to decouple the dynamics of the tailless airplane in the three axes, B^* is chosen to be identity so the we can command the pitch, roll and yaw attitudes of the airplane independently. Therefore, the control selector $CS(Mach, altitude)$ is,

$$CS = \begin{bmatrix} M_{\alpha} + 0.1Z_{\alpha} & \cdots & M_r + 0.1Z_r \\ L_{\alpha} & \cdots & L_r \\ N_{\alpha} & \cdots & N_r \end{bmatrix}^{\#} \quad (9)$$

where $\#$ is the pseudo-inverse operation.

4.1.2 Dynamic Inversion Controller: With the control selector CS included, we now have the following generalized control variable dynamics:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{M}_{cv} \\ \dot{L}_{cv} \\ \dot{N}_{cv} \end{bmatrix} = \kappa \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \\ r \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \dot{M}_{cv cmd} \\ \dot{L}_{cv cmd} \\ \dot{N}_{cv cmd} \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

with

$$\kappa = \begin{bmatrix} M_{\alpha} + 0.1Z_{\alpha} & \cdots & M_r + 0.1Z_r \\ L_{\alpha} & \cdots & L_r \\ N_{\alpha} & \cdots & N_r \end{bmatrix}$$

The desired closed-loop dynamic is chosen so that the vehicle will tend to maintain its equilibrium position and to decouple its longitudinal and lateral axes. Namely, an increase in angle of attack α or pitch rate q will cause a negative pitch acceleration opposing such increase. The same is true with the roll rate p and yaw rate r . A positive roll or yaw rate p or r will tend to create a negative rolling or yawing moments $L\dot{C}V$ or $dot{N}CV$ respectively to stabilize the airplane:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{M}_{cv} \\ \dot{L}_{cv} \\ \dot{N}_{cv} \end{bmatrix}_d = \nu \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ q \\ \beta \\ p \\ r \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \dot{M}_{cv cmd} \\ \dot{L}_{cv cmd} \\ \dot{N}_{cv cmd} \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

with ν being the desired dynamics

$$\begin{bmatrix} -0.25 & -2.5 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -2.5 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2.5 & 0 & -2.5 \end{bmatrix}_d$$

From Equations 8 and 11, the inverse dynamic control law is,

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{M}CV_{cmd} \\ \dot{L}CV_{cmd} \\ \dot{N}CV_{cmd} \end{bmatrix} = (\nu - \kappa) \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \\ r \end{bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

Thus the dynamic-inversion, full state feedback control law for the inner loop is $k = \nu - \kappa$. For the plant model obtained at 15,000 feet, Mach 0.4, the closed-loop eigenvalues are shown in Table 4

Table 4: Closed-Loop Eigenvalues

Eigenvalues λ	Damping ζ	Frequency ω (Rad/Sec)
-0.72	1	2.5
-2.50	1	2.5
-2.50	1	2.5
-1.3+j0.94	0.81	1.6
-1.3-j0.94	0.81	1.6

4.2. Outer-Loop Design

With airplane dynamics in the design envelope equalized in the inner-loop, we then proceed with the outer-loop design. Since the inner-loop plant has dynamics that are similar in the flight envelope, we seek to design a single dynamic controller for the inner-loop plant. The design objectives for the outer-loop controller is the handling quality performance in command tracking, and robustness to plant uncertainties. We formulate our design problem in the frame work of structured singular synthesis, or μ synthesis [4].

A synthesis model consisting of the plant model, ideal model, performance weighting, input weightings, and axis transformations is formed to design a μ -synthesis controller. The plant model used to formulate the outer-loop design problem is the closed inner-loop of the central linear model of the airplane. The eigenvalues of this inner-loop are shown in Table 4 In order to achieve our handling quality performance in command tracking, we first try to match the closed-loop response of the airplane to an ideal model. we then use a pre-filter that includes the flying qualities dynamics and inverted closed-loop plant responses to achieve desired responses. The ideal model have the following transfer functions:

$$\begin{bmatrix} q_i \\ \beta_i \\ \dot{\mu}_i \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{2.5}{s+2.5} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1.21}{s^2+1.76s+1.21} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{2.5}{s+2.5} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} q_c \\ \beta_c \\ \dot{\mu}_c \end{bmatrix}$$

Since we do not expect the tailless airplane to have great yawing moment, sideslip ideal model is slower than that of the pitch rate and roll rate ideal models so that control surface usage is reasonable. The response errors in pitch rate q , sideslip β , and roll rate $\dot{\mu}$ in stability axis are defined as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} q_{error} \\ \beta_{error} \\ \dot{\mu}_{error} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} q_i - q_{sensor} \\ \beta_i - \beta_{sensor} \\ \dot{\mu}_i - \dot{\mu}_{sensor} \end{bmatrix}$$

4.2.1 Performance Weighting: In this H_∞ optimization design, we only want to minimize the H_{infty} of the tracking error over some range of frequency. We want to match the ideal transient response with little steady state error. The transient response error of the physical airplane is more dominant toward the lower frequency range of between 0.01 rad/sec to 10 rad/sec. The pilot stick input is likely inside this frequency range. Therefore, we can place more emphasis for optimization over this range of frequency. This frequency range as shown in Figure 2 also adequately covers the dynamic response of our ideal model.

4.2.2 Control Input Weighting: The input uncertainties at low frequencies are less than the uncertainties at high frequencies. High-pass frequency weighting can therefore be used to reflect this. The control input weightings for the three generalized control inputs are the same and have the transfer functions of $\frac{2(s+2)}{(s+20)}$. An axis transformation is needed to convert the body-axis sensor output values to stability-axis values. The transformation T_2 converts the sensors outputs $[\alpha \ q \ \beta \ p \ r]^T$ to the stability-axis

Figure 2: Performance Weighting

outputs $[q \ \beta \ \dot{\mu}]^T$ for tracking errors calculations. Similarly, a transformation T_1 converts the outputs of the controller into body-axis rate commands $[q_c \ \beta_c \ \dot{\mu}_c]^T$

$$T_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & \cos\alpha & \sin\alpha \end{bmatrix}$$

and

$$T_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -\sin\alpha & \cos\alpha \\ 0 & -\cos\alpha & \sin\alpha \end{bmatrix}$$

4.2.3 μ -synthesis Design: The μ -synthesis design is an iterative process that consist of two parts. The first part involves finding a H_∞ controller K . The second part involves performing the μ -analysis to find the upper bound of μ of the closed-loop system. In the process, the output and input frequency scalings D^{-1} and D are found. The scalings are then appended to the synthesis model. A second H_∞ controller K replacing the first controller is calculated for the appended synthesis model. μ -analysis is performed again on this system. The second scalings D^{-1} and D are found which are combined with the first set of scalings to produce new input and output scalings to be appended to the synthesis model. The procedure is repeated until the upper bound of μ is less than one. Balanced truncation [10] is then applied to the 28th-order controller to reduced controller order to 10.

4.3. Controller Evaluation

The closed-loop airplane performance is evaluated at flight conditions having mach number ranging from 0.3 to 0.5 and altitude ranging from 10,000 to 20,000 feet.

4.3.1 Time History Simulation: Linear simulation of the closed inner, outer loop for the central flight condition are shown in Figures 3, 4, 5. These responses of pitch rate, sideslip, and roll rate to step commands are close to the ideal model responses.

4.3.2 Flying Qualities: Flying qualities of the tailless airplane are evaluated by appending a prefilter of desired fly quality dynamics to the closed-loop plant. The low order, equivalent system (LOES) of transfer functions from the pilot commands to q, β , and $\dot{\mu}$ are then found. The values of closed-loop ζ_{sp} , ζ_d , T_r , ω_d , ω_{sp} , and $\tau_{\theta, \mu, \beta}$ with respect to the flying qualities levels are shown in the Figures 6, 7,

Figure 3: Pitch Rate Linear Response

Figure 4: Sideslip Linear Response

Figure 5: Roll Rate Linear Response

Figure 6: Dutch Roll ζ_d & ω_d

Figure 7: Delay time

Figure 8: Roll Time Constant

and 8 Due to the presence of high-order dynamics in the actual system, bounds must be placed on the mismatch between the LOES and the actual system over the frequency range. A mismatch that exceeds the bounds could result in the pilot downgrading the predicted flying quality level due to the added dynamics experienced by the pilots. Since the pilot is most sensitive to the dynamics in the frequency range of 1 to 4 rad/sec, the bounds are most restricted in this frequency range.

4.4. Robust Analysis

For structured uncertainties, the stability derivatives uncertainties are shown in Table 5. All control derivatives are taken to have 15% uncertainties bounds. Figure 9 can be

Table 5: Parameter Uncertainty Bounds

Stability Derivatives	Uncertainty Bounds
	Δ_{struct}
Z_α	2%
M_α	4%
Y_β	15%
L_β	10%
L_p	30%
L_r	20%
N_β	30%
N_p	50%
N_r	15%

simplified into block form: If the μ bound of the transfer function $T_{wz} \leq 1$ then the system remains stable despite of the above multivariable uncertainties. Figure 11 shows

